

Determination of Heavy Metals in Powdered Milk on Sale in Wudil, Kano, Nigeria

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Abstract

The awareness about the safety of food is increasing in several parts of the world as many toxic contaminants tend to enter into the food chain. Milk has been the nature's most perfect food for mankind, since it is the sole source of nutrient for new born mammals. Milk is essential for growth and maintenance of good health. Contamination of milk is transferred to animals through direct exposure, polluted water, crops grown on irrigated sewage water, industrial effluents and feeding from recycled animal wastes. Heavy metals are probably the most harmful and insidious contaminants, due to their biological non-biodegradable nature and their potential to cause adverse effects at certain level of exposure and absorption even in their lowest form. The presence of trace metals in milk depend on many factors, such as environmental condition, method of production and processing. Some of the health risks of these trace metals include: hypertension, heart palpitation, increased risk of colon cancer, muscle cramps, especially in pregnant women, impaired growth, nervousness and insomnia. The results obtained in this study showed that mean concentrations of heavy metals in the milk samples are in decreasing order: Zn>Fe> Cu>Pb>Cr.

Keywords: Heavy metal, milk, concentration, non-biodegradable, health risk.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent time, there has been increasing concern about the presence and levels of numerous chemical contaminants in food used for human consumption. Food processing equipment and containers have been recognized as a source of trace metals such as Fe, Cu, Pb and Cr in the processed foods (Onianwa et al., 2001). Trace metals are commonly cited as significant contaminants because of their general environmental ubiquity and ease of assimilation in the food chain. Trace metals are significant in nutrition, either for their essential nature or their toxicity (Khaniki and Reze, 2005). Although it is difficult to classify trace metals into essential and toxic groups, yet it is well known fact that an essential metal becomes toxic at sufficiently high intakes (Khurshid and Qureshi, 1984).

However, elements such as copper and zinc, although essential for life processes when in traces, have adverse effect when ingested in higher amounts. Lead, arsenic, cadmium and methyl mercury are non-essential and potentially highly toxic metals (Chisolm, 1984). They may be found in minute and variable but measurable amounts in food, drinking water and ambient air. Cumulative poisoning due to ingestion of food containing elements such as lead or arsenic over long period is probably rare (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991).

Rapid industrialization, use of agricultural chemicals and automobile exhaust fumes have increased the toxic levels of heavy metals in the environment and affected all the global air, water and food. Human population is directly affected through the food chain (Zamir and Hussain, 2001). By accumulating metals, plants can transfer heavy metal pollutants from soil into the food chain, and this accumulation is one of the most serious environmental concerns of the present day, not only because of the toxicity of many of these metals to the crops themselves but also because of the potential harmful effects they could have on animals and human health (Radojevie and Bashkin, 1999).

Milk has been the nature's most perfect food for mankind, since it is the sole source of nutrient for new born mammals. Since the domestication of cattle and the adoption of pastoralist agriculture, milk has become the most versatile of the animal-derived food commodities and is a component of the diet in many physical forms. Milk is complex mixture of emulsified lipids and

protein, in addition to other dissolved components such as lactose, vitamins and minerals (Luu et al., 1998). The composition and physical characteristics of milk vary from species to species, reflecting the dietary needs of the young mammal (Vannam and Sutherland, 1994). Milk proteins are of two distinct types, whey proteins (serum proteins) and caseins. Caseins constitute over 80% of the total protein of milk, although the relative proportion of whey protein to casein varies according to the stage of lactation. Milk fat is generally regarded as being of complex composition.

Milk contains a large number of minor components and micronutrients including urea, enzymes and vitamins. Milk is a source of the fat soluble vitamins C, B, B₂, B₆, B₁₂, pantothenic acid, niacin, biotin and folic acid. The vitamin content of milk is strongly modified by losses during processing and storage (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991). Milk is essential for growth and maintenance of good health, contamination is transferred to animals via direct exposure, polluted water, crops grown on irrigated sewage water, industrial effluents and feeding from recycled animal wastes (Norman and Edmondson, 1990). According to Muller (1980), the greatest concern of feeding recycled animal wastes is due to accumulation of macro minerals (Ca, Si, Fe, trace elements (Cu, Mn, Zn, Se), heavy metals (Pb, Hg, Cd), medicines (antibiotics, sulfa, coccidiostats, etc), and mycotoxins, preservatives, insecticides, etc. The only adverse effect found so far, however, has been copper toxicity in sheep fed litter from poultry that received copper supplements as growth stimulants.

Since the second quarter of the 20th century outstanding advances were made in understanding the nutritional significance of the mineral composition of most animal feeds. The major inorganic components of milk are said to be important both to human nutrition and also as stabilizers of the milk system (Cerbulis, 1969). Milk plays an important role in the diet of a growing child and the mature humans especially at old age. All nutritionists agree that a regular intake of milk is beneficial to growing children (Davidson et al., 1975). In the world today, milk is the only single food that contains the entire essential nutrient in significant quantity. As a complete food easily given, easily digested and absorbed, milk is an ideal food for invalids, especially for patients with acute illness (Davidson et al., 1975).

Milk is thus regarded as a complex mixture of varying quantities of lipids, protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and water. Milk protein is of very high nutritional value and is also highly digestible, although digestibility can be reduced by processing (Vannam and Sutherland, 1994). Processing can also lead to nutrient loss. Milk provides about half the daily protein requirement for teenage humans and about 60% of the entire requirement for the growing children of 0-6 years, about 40% for lactating human (Schmidt and Van Vleck, 1974). Thus about 1.4 dm³ of milk is required for both adults and infants daily. Milk also provides unsaturated fatty acids necessary for digestion and also acids as a vehicle for carrying fat soluble vitamins (Lambert, 1975).

The minerals in milk as determined in the ash shows that the principal inorganic constituents of retail whole milk are 114 mg/100g Ca, 12 mg/100g mg, 55 mg/100g Na, (Florence et al., 1985). Some of these minerals are essential for reproduction, human growth, development and body fluid regulation. Iron and iodine are present in low quantity (Ling, 1956).

Effect of diet on the mineral composition of milk could occur since some mineral composition varies with the diet type taken by various types of milk producing animals. Some minerals like iodine, zinc, molybdenum, manganese increase in concentration in milk, if there is increased intake beyond the normal dietary intake of the element; the reverse is the case with elements like iron, copper and iodine, whose increase in the diet does not record a marked rise in their concentrations.

Lead and copper were significantly higher, while Zn was significantly lower in cows fed with commercial formula. The metal content of milk may be altered by processing. Lead from water and airborne sources have been shown to accumulate in agricultural areas leading to increased concentrations in agricultural produce and farm animals (ATSDR, 1993)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and analysis

Nine samples of different instant powdered sachet milk were randomly selected from Wudil metropolis before their expiry dates and stored in air tight containers at ambient temperature. 5g each of Powdered Milk samples were weighed into a 50ml beaker. 10ml of nitric acid was added and heated up to 80°C for about 30 minutes. After cooling the mixture, 5ml of 70% perchloric acid was added and heated again to 250°C with occasional shaking till white fumes evolved. The solution was cooled and filtered into a 50ml volumetric flask and made up to mark with deionized water. The concentrations of the heavy metals were determined using the BUCK Scientific VEP 210 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Mean and standard deviation of heavy metal concentrations(mg/kg) of milk samples selected from different locations in Wudil town, Kano State, Nigeria are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of heavy metal concentrations (mg/kg) of milk samples

Samples	Cr	Pb	Cu	Zn	Fe
Mw1	ND	0.083±0.01	0.223±0.01	16.49±3.02	1.119±0.26
Mw2	ND	0.116±0.01	0.220±0.01	15.68±0.02	1.188±0.71
Mw3	ND	0.012±0.003	0.216±0.02	20.58±4.06	1.491±0.86
Mw4	ND	0.068±0.01	0.045±0.03	11.89±2.60	4.976±1.86
Mw5	ND	0.083±0.02	0.278±0.03	18.65±3.66	1.790±0.72
Mw6	ND	0.25±0.11	0.133±0.03	17.63±0.88	2.290±1.03
Mw7	ND	0.04±0.01	0.082±0.03	18.62±1.66	2.055±0.86
Mw8	ND	0.02±0.003	0.083±0.01	22.69±3.62	1.611±0.20
Mw9	ND	0.097±0.03	0.061±0.03	14.58±3.02	0.022±0.003

Figure 1: Concentration of Lead in the Milk samples

The concentrations of lead range from 0.002-0.116 mg/kg as shown in fig.1 above. The highest concentration of lead was recorded in Mw2 (0.116 mg/kg) and the lowest in Mw1 (0.002mg/kg). Other values obtained were 0.083, 0.003, 0.068, 0.083, 0.004 and 0.097 mg/kg. The values obtained

were below the maximum residue limit (2.0 mg/kg) set by the Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) and NAFDAC. Similar results were reported by Moges, where values ranging from 0.038-0.1688 mg/kg were obtained for milk samples in Harar, Ethiopia(A Moges, 2014). However, Tona et al., reported much lower values (0.0025 - 0.0061 mg/kg) in different milk products sold in Ogbomosho, South-Western, Nigeria .The presence of lead in these brands of powdered milk could be attributed to the exposure of lactating cows from which powdered milk was made to contaminated fodder, climatic factors, use of agro-chemicals and very importantly drinking water (A Moges, 2014).

Figure2: Concentration of Copper in the Milk samples

The concentrations of copper in the brands of milk range from 0.045-0.278 mg/kg as shown in fig. 2. The highest concentrations of copper was recorded in Mw5 (0.278 mg/kg) and the lowest in Mw4 (0.045 mg/kg). Other values obtained were 0.2233 mg/kg, 0.2204 mg/kg, 0.2156 mg/kg, 0.133mg/kg, 0.0824mg/kg, 0.0834mg/kg and 0.0611mg/kg. B Sarkar, reported that deficiency in copper causes many hematological diseases such as anemia, leukopenia and neutrophils. Akpanyung 2006, reported 0.60 - 1.51 mg/kg of copper in various powdered milk While, Lutfullah et al., 2014 and Lawal et al., 2015 reported values ranging from 0.10 - 1.40 mg/kg and 5.30 - 7.10 mg/kg respectively. Burch and Hahn had earlier observed that milk and dairy products are poor sources of copper, which concurs with this finding (RD Burch and H Hahn, 1983)

Figure 3: Concentration of Iron in the Milk samples.

The concentration of iron in the milk samples range from 1.119-4.976mg/kg as shown in fig. 3. The highest concentration of iron was recorded in Mw4 (4.976 mg/kg) and the lowest in Mw1 (1.119mg/kg). Other values obtained were 1.188mg/kg, 1.491mg/kg, 1.790mg/kg, 2.290mg/kg, 2.055mg/kg, 1.611mg/kg and 0.022mg/kg. The concentrations of iron in the

various brands of powdered milk samples were statistically significant. Similar results were reported by Lutfullah et al., 2014 where values ranging from 1.30 - 4.30 mg/kg were obtained in various powdered milk samples. Akpanyung 2006, reported values ranging from 9.02-11.82 mg of iron per 100g in different powdered milk samples. The values obtained in this study were below the recommended dietary allowance (10-15 mg/kg) set by Food and Nutrition Board(FNB) 2001.

Figure 4: Concentration of Zinc in the Milk samples

The Zinc content of powdered milk from fig.4 above compared favorably with the manufacturer's claim that it contains 17mg/kg Zn. Zinc was the next abundant mineral in powdered milk, which has the highest concentration 11.89mg/kg and a lowest concentration of 2.69mg/kg.

Zinc is an essential trace element for humans. Its deficiency as well as excess is harmful. Recent research has shown that zinc is extremely important especially in fetal development and the nutrition of infants. The adult human body contains about 2.3 g of zinc which occurs mostly in over 100 enzymes. The normal daily requirement for zinc is 15 mg for adult and 5 mg for children. Zinc plays a role in carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism and in the synthesis and breakdown of DNA. Because of these functions, zinc deficiency in the fetus will result in retarded growth malformation of body, and chromosomal abnormalities. A zinc deficiency after birth may result in dwarfism, poor appetite and mental lethargy,

CONCLUSION

Results of the Trace Metals analysis showed that none the samples analyzed is above the permissible limit. The results obtained also showed that chromium was not detected in the milk samples. Thus, the concentrations of the studied trace elements evaluated in the current study are within the safety tolerable limit set by FAO/WHO, hence recommended for consumption. The mean concentration of the heavy metals is in the decreasing order: Zn>Fe> Cu>Pb>Cr.

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